

ON THE CORROSION RESISTANCE OF SOME P/M FERROUS MATERIALS AFTER STEAM TREATMENT

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Abstract

A commonly accepted opinion is that steam treatment increases the corrosion resistance of P/M ferrous materials. To confirm the scanty literature data the behaviour of steam treated materials has been investigated. The test samples have been pistons for refrigerator compressors, namely P/M parts typically steam treated. The corrosion resistance has been checked by different methods: evaluation of corrosion resistance by means of potentiodynamic tests and corrosion potential measurements in different aggressive environments; weight loss measurements in H_2SO_4 solutions at different concentration; salt fog spray tests, according to the corresponding standard. The steam treated samples have been compared with only sintered parts and fully dense low-carbon steel. The materials have been characterized by measurement of density and hardness, by evaluation of pore features by image analysis, by EDAX analysis of oxide distribution. It has been found that steam treatment improves corrosion resistance in NaCl solution while the effect is modest in H_2SO_4 solutions. The weight loss test indicated that corrosion products, which remain entrapped inside the inner porosity, hide the actual loss of material originated by corrosion. The collapse of particles, when the sintering necks fail, is the reason of a “jumping” course of the results. As to weight loss, steam treated sample are competitive with fully dense low-carbon steel. The salt fog spray test evidenced a dramatic difference between steam treated and untreated materials. The positive results attributable to a steam treatment effect are weakened by the presence of some Fe_2O_3 , on the outer surfaces. This unwanted oxide frequently appear on steam treated P/M parts in case of not-perfect equipment or incomplete process

control, at any stage. By and large, the results confirm the well-accepted idea that steam oxidation moderately improves corrosion resistance.

Key words: Corrosion resistance; P/M parts; Sintering; Steam treatment

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1. Introduction

Long time ago, in 1942, Lenel, [1], described for the first time this method, to improve some characteristics of ferrous materials. Especially in the USA, industrial applications of the process were remarkable already at the beginning of Fifties. In the same decade, the protective effect of a magnetite layer was known, [2, 3, 4]. Useful indications on the steam treatment process can be found in various literature, [5 - 12]; Gallo and Sergi. [13] investigated also the kinetics of oxide layer growth. Several authors, when listing the advantages attributable to steam oxidation usually include also corrosion resistance. This statement, however, is not supported by same numerical indication. It seems that only Fedrizzi, Molinari et al. [14, 15], carried out a specific research work focused on the improvement of corrosion resistance depending on a continuous layer of ferrous-ferric oxide formed on all surfaces of P/M ferrous components. They found that corrosion resistance of steam treated ferrous materials is mainly defined by the Fe_3O_4 layer and that the possible differences depend on quantity of oxide present. For a more complete survey on the influence of oxide layer on the corrosion resistance of iron-base sintered materials, a specific research has been started, aimed at characterizing any possible effect of different chemical composition and density effects, if any. In this work the results achieved in a first phase, focused on plain sintered steel, are presented.

2. Investigated materials

The tests of resistance to aggressive environments have been carried out on P/M parts that are typically steam-treated: pistons for refrigerator compressors. The samples for testing, taken from an industrial lot, compacted at $6.4 \div 6,5 \text{ g/cm}^3$ average density, sintered at 1393 K for 1500 s, and steam treated in a batch furnace at 823 K, for 2.5 hours, have been characterized. The base mix includes an atomized iron powder, with 0.3 % graphite and 0.5% MnS, added for improving machinability, plus 0.75% of compaction lubricant.

3. Experimental methods

The investigation techniques include:

- determination of average density;
- weight increase due to steam treatment,
- hardness and microhardness;
- optical (or light) microscopy, shortly OM;
- scanning electron microscopy, shortly SEM;
- determination of pore properties by image and quantitative analysis;
- evaluation of oxide thickness on the outer surfaces;
- X-rays analysis;
- Evaluation of corrosion resistance by means of potentiodynamic polarization curves and corrosion potential measurements in 0.05 M NaCl and 0.05M H₂SO₄ solutions;
- weight loss measurements in H₂SO₄ solutions at different concentrations: 0.05M, 0.025M, 0.005 M;
- salt fog spray test, according to the standard ISO 9227 (1990).

4. Experimental results

The data characterizing the investigated materials are reported in Table 1. The pore fraction after steam treatment has dropped to about 3.5%; some pore cross-sections are completely covered by oxide. The oxidation even at part core corresponds to the customary effect of the process. On the average, on the outer surfaces of pistons the thickness of oxide layer is about 4.0 μm. Especially on the outer surfaces, the layers appear as formed by two different oxides. In particular, the more outer layer is porous and lighter in colour, whereas the oxide layer directly grown on the ferrous matrix appears darker, nearly exempt from inner porosity, and well adhering to the base metal. The microstructures are presented in Figures 1, 2 and 3. Microhardness ranges, on cross sections, are: 120 ÷ 150 on the sintered pistons and 170 ÷ 235 on the steam treated pistons. The original particles of MnS can be clearly distinguished. By means of energy dispersion X-rays spectroscopy it has been found that the steam oxidation process caused some transformation of MnS

into FeS and Mn and Fe oxides (Figure 4). The so formed constituents remain frequently embedded inside the oxide layer. At a small distance from pores, inside the matrix, only iron is present. The X-rays diffractogram, Figure 5, shows that Fe₃O₄ and Fe₂O₃ are present inside the oxide layer. Also reflections of the ferritic substratum are evident. The pore roundness has been evaluated by the formula: $p_r = p^2/(4\pi A)$, being p the pore perimeter and A the pore area.

	State	Average density g/cm ³	Estimated density g/cm ³	Weight increase %	Pore roundness	HV 5 Hardness	HV 0.05 Hardness (inside)	
	as sintered		6.45	6.5 (A)		1.8 (A)	95 (A)	135 (A)
		6.6 (B)		1.9 (B)		98 (B)		
		6.3 (C)		1.95 (C)		84 (C)		
		6.5 (D)		2.0 (D)		76 (D)		
steam treated			6.71	6.75 (A, B)	4.0 ÷ 4.1	1,8 (A)	174 (A)	195 (A)
				6.6 (C)		1,8 (B)	173 (B)	
				6.75 (D)		1,9 (C, D)		

Table 1 – Physical and porosity properties, weight change and hardness measured on the tested samples

Figure 1 – Microstructure, as sintered material

Figure 2 - Microstructure after steam treatment, A zone

Figure 3 - Microstructure after steam treatment, at part core

Figure 4 – X-Ray mapping of Fe, Mn, O and S after the changes due to oxidation and sulphur transfer

Figure 5 – Diffractogram on the outer surface of steam treated pistons, showing the presence of Fe₂O₃

4.1 Electrochemical tests

The corrosion behaviour of the specimens (complete pistons, either as sintered or steam treated) was investigated by polarization tests and corrosion potential measurements, both performed in aerated solutions (0.05 M H₂SO₄ and 0.05 M NaCl) at 25 °C. Polarization tests were carried out in the potential range $-1000 \div +600$ mV at a scan rate at $0.5 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Corrosion potential measurements were performed as a function of time for a period of 24 h. The potentials are reported with respect to a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Figure 6 shows the polarization curves recorded in aerated 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution. By considering the anodic branch of the curves, a rapid increase of current density is observed above the corrosion potential (-580 mV/SCE) as a result of metal dissolution reaction. At potentials > 400 mV/SCE the anodic current density increases gradually to a near steady-state value: $30 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for the untreated specimen, $20 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for the oxidized one. This behaviour is attributable to the formation of a corrosion products surface layer, as revealed by SEM characterization. The poor corrosion behaviour of the oxidized sample is confirmed by the corrosion potential vs. time measurements reported in Figure 7. As a matter of

fact, the corrosion potential of the oxidized specimen exhibit a rapid decay within the first hour of exposure to the aggressive environment, then reaching a stationary value (-580 mV/SCE) close to that of the untreated one (-595 mV/SCE). Better corrosion performances are evidenced in neutral environments where iron oxides are more stable [16]. Figure 8 shows the polarization curves recorded in aerated 0.05 M NaCl solution. It can be seen that the corrosion potential of the oxidized sample is shifted toward less negative values (-550 mV/SCE) with respect to the untreated one (-700 mV/SCE). Moreover, the anodic current density for the untreated specimen is twice (≈ 11 mA \cdot cm $^{-2}$) in comparison to the oxidized one (≈ 5.5 mA \cdot cm $^{-2}$). The results of polarization test agree with those of the corrosion potential vs. time measurements, as evidenced in Figure 9.

Figure 6 – Polarization curves recorded on ferrous specimens in aerated 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution at 25 °C

Figure 7 – Corrosion potential vs. exposure time in 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution at 25 °C for ferrous samples

Figure 8 - Polarization curves recorded on ferrous specimens in aerated 0.05 M NaCl solution at 25 °C

Figure 9 – Corrosion potential vs. exposure time in 0.05 M NaCl solution at 25 °C for ferrous samples

4.2 Weight loss test

This test has been performed in H₂SO₄ solutions at different concentrations: 0.05M, 0.025M, 0.005M. The mass loss (per unit surface) versus time may be taken as an index of corrosion rate. For a better assessment of the influence of steam treatment on corrosion resistance a comparison with plain (low carbon) steel has also been carried out (Figure 10). When necessary, for the only sintered pistons, the tests have been stopped as the “instant” mass dropped to half the initial one.

Sintered specimen: Figure 11 shows that corrosion rate increases versus time, following an irregular trend, that appears anomalous after 5 days. Presumably, this anomalous trend depends on corrosion products, which form on the outer part surface, without adhering to the metallic substratum. When these products detach, a new “fresh” surface is exposed to the aggressive solution and corrosion products form again because of the increase of corrosion rate. On the other side, if corrosion products are formed inside pores, they remain entrapped, thereby altering the actual trend of weight loss versus time.

Figure 10 – Weight loss in 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution for steam treated sample and fully dense low carbon steel

Steam treated pistons: as can be seen in Figure 11 the corrosion rate is high at the beginning of test and after this transient it remains nearly constant. The initial behaviour can be attributed to the dissolution of the porous hematite layer, observed by OM and SEM, and confirmed by X-rays investigation. Once this layer is removed, the corrosion process follows a law that is dictated by the good properties of Fe₃O₄ layer; also the corrosion products, presumably, tend to adhere to the matrix, and to protect it from further corrosion attack. Both phenomena contribute to render constant the corrosion rate. Due to the very small value of residual porosity, any disturbing effect attributable to corrosion products entrapped inside pores can be excluded.

Figure 11 – Weight loss in 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution for only sintered and steam treated samples

The behaviour of both porous materials appears rather similar at the beginning, namely for the first day. After this exposure period, a different behaviour is observed, which persists till to the end of test (Figure 12). This phenomenon can be attributed to the poor corrosion properties of hematite. Once this layer has been removed, the decrease of mass loss per unit surface can be ascribed to the good corrosion properties of Fe₃O₄ layer. The irregular behaviour, exhibited by the as sintered pistons, is presumably due to some sudden detachment of particle remains, from the surface zones, when the neck section formed on sintering decreases to zero. If the detachment of particles occurs inside pores, no weight loss is detected. The tests in

variously H_2SO_4 diluted solutions show that a “threshold” concentration is required to attack the oxide layers (Figure 13).

Figure 12 – Weight loss in 0.05 M H_2SO_4 solution for only sintered and steam treated samples. Mobile averages

4.3 Salt fog spray test

This test has been carried out according to the standard ISO 9227 1990(E) [17]. One as sintered piston and one steam treated piston have been kept into the chamber for 7 hours. The corrosion attack effects have been evaluated by visual observation and by image analysis. Both methods agree: the corrosion areas on the upper surface of the sintered specimen are more extended than on the same surface of the steam treated one. The results of image analysis, to guess the corrosion areas, are 79% on the sintered piston and 49% on the steam treated sample, respectively. Even the depth of corrosion is different, with the higher one

corresponding to the as sintered piston. Figures 14 and 15 show the appearance of upper surfaces of the tested specimens.

Figure 13 – Weight loss in H₂SO₄ solutions at different concentrations. Steam treated pistons

5. Concluding remarks

The different tests show that steam treatment is an effective method to improve the corrosion resistance of ferrous porous materials. However, the improvement may be weakened by the presence of a Fe₂O₃ layer. This harmful oxide may form if H₂O/H₂ ratio exceeds a safety limit. This situation may happen, in case of improper equipment or incorrect steam treatment process, at any stage. By and large, the results agree with the few data existing in the literature. Corrosion potential measurements and mass loss tests in acidic solution show at first a low corrosion resistance for steam treated material. This behaviour can be ascribed to the preferential dissolution of a thin and porous hematite outer layer formed on the outer surfaces of the parts, as evidenced by SEM and X-ray analysis. Once this layer is removed, the good properties of Fe₃O₄ layer appear. As to weight loss, steam treated samples are competitive with fully dense low-carbon steel (Figure 10). In case of simply sintered samples, the corrosion products remain entrapped inside the inner porosity, thus hiding the actual effect of aggressive the environment. The steam oxidation process caused

some transformation of MnS into FeS and Mn and Fe oxides (Figure 4). The so formed constituents remain frequently embedded inside the oxide layer in the pores. This last point should be investigated more deeply, because the positive influence of MnS addition on material's machinability may decrease.

Figure 14 – Upper surface of as sintered piston after 7 hours testing in salt fog spray chamber

Figure 15 – Upper surface of as sintered piston after 7 hours testing in salt fog spray chamber

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